

EFFECT OF FIBER DISTRIBUTION ON COMBINED COMPRESSION-TORSIONAL RESPONSE OF HYBRID COMPOSITES

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1. Introduction

❖ Uncertainties in the composite compressive strength:

- Two glass/carbon hybrid composites were modelled using the finite element software ABAQUS CAE.
- The RVEs of hybrid models consist of 36 carbon fibers, one glass fiber and Vinyl ester resin. They differ only in their fiber distribution.
- Fibers are assumed to be elastic with no misalignments and the matrix is assigned with a nonlinear elastic-plastic behaviour.
- The interface is modelled as perfectly bonded.
- The axial combined loading analysis was carried out for various values of loading ratio ($\Delta/R\theta$) in displacement/rotational control method.

1). Symmetric fiber distribution (C36G1 model)

2). Un-symmetric fiber distribution (C36G1S model)

2. Modelling

3. Results

- The combined loading response curve is highly nonlinear showing strong interaction between compression and shear.
- The failure initiated in shear with the yielding of matrix under the influence of compression induced shear. The failure in compression occurred later due to splitting of interface in the micro-buckled kink band.

4. Conclusion

- Fiber distribution played a significant role in the combined loading response of the hybrid composites
- The model with symmetric fiber distribution had larger values of compressive stress and failure strain compared to that of the un-symmetric fiber distribution
- Having an un-symmetrical fiber distribution and/or presence of external shear is identical to introducing a geometric imperfection in to the composite
- The addition of external shear on to the model with un-symmetric fiber distribution decreased the compressive strength further
- For a range of loading ratios, the combined loading failure envelop has showed the linear trend followed by the drop in compressive strength from pure compression, tending towards pure torsion, with increasing shear
- The lower bound of failure was obtained to be the failure in shear, for both the cases of fiber distribution

